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Green Marketing: Way to Sustainable Development

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Abstract:

Green marketing is a modern concept emerged in the global market and has gained popularity in India and other nations. Today, with an increase in environmental issues, consumer preferences have shifted from traditional products to eco-friendly ones. So it has become essential for industries to create an environmentally conscious image among consumers and society. This will help them to attract green consumers and protect environment from hazardous effects of industrialization. Despite its growing popularity, in the late 1980s, green marketing faced serious obstacles, because many industries make false claims by labeling their products and services as eco-friendly. Industries can achieve the green goal and increase the sales of green products with the help of the Green Marketing Mix (4P) and by focusing on messaging attributes such as price and quality. Going green helps a company win the trust and loyalty of green consumers. Moreover, it is seen as a crucial instrument for sustainable development. The concept of green marketing is now included in academics as well. In this research paper, the main focus is made on the concept of green marketing, green marketing mix, green marketing strategies, needs, benefits, and challenges in green marketing. Further, the way to achieve sustainable development through green marketing is also explained here.

Keywords: Green marketing, Green marketing mix, Green marketing strategy, Green marketing strategy matrix, Sustainable development.

Introduction:

In the early 1980s, the term green marketing, also known as environmental or ecological marketing, gained popularity in Europe when certain products were found hazardous to the environment. As a result, green products that were less harmful to the environment were introduced. In 1975, the first workshop on ecological marketing was hosted by the American Marketing Association (AMA), and the first book on green marketing, titled Ecological Marketing, was published. In India, green marketing was started in the late 1990s when the Government of India launched the Eco-Mark Scheme in 1991. The main objective of the scheme is to make consumers aware of eco-friendly products and encourage them to purchase these products. Thus, green marketing means developing and promoting those goods and services that have no or minimal adverse effect on the environment. Thus, it is a holistic marketing concept wherein the creation, usage, and disposal of goods and services are done in a manner that is less hazardous to the environment. Today, both marketers and consumers are in need of moving towards eco-friendly goods and services.

Objective of Study:

The Study aims:

1. To comprehend the term green marketing.
2. To understand the development of green marketing.
3. To gain insight into the green marketing mix.
4. To get knowledge about green marketing strategy.

Research Methodology:

Secondary source of data is used in this research paper. The secondary information has been collected from various published resources such as articles, journals, reports, reference books, and websites. Further, the research is descriptive and exploratory in nature.

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Basic Terminologies:

Marketing: Marketing is an array of activities that a company performs to encourage the purchase and sale of a good or service. It involves advertising, sales promotion, public relations, and building and maintaining customer relationships.

Green Marketing: It is the promotion of goods and services based on their environmental benefits. These products and services are sustainable, energy-sufficient, and less hazardous to the environment.

Green Products: Green products are manufactured through green technology and are safe for the environment and human health during their production, use, and disposal. They are made from renewable, recyclable, and sustainable materials. The main aim of green products is to conserve natural resources and energy, make minimum use of toxic agents and waste, and reduce pollution by lowering carbon footprints.

Green Services: Green services refer to eco-friendly services that reduce negative impacts on the environment. These services focus on sustainability, energy efficiency, and minimizing pollution and resource consumption. They can span industries like energy, transportation, agriculture, waste management, infrastructure, etc.

Green Consumers: Green consumers, also known as green customers, are individuals who buy eco-friendly products and help protect the natural environment. They purchase products that are recyclable, biodegradable, organic, or made with sustainable materials so that no or minimal harm can be caused to the environment. In short, they are environmentally conscious.

Green Marketing:

Meaning

Green marketing is the promotion of goods or services that are eco-friendly or have a positive effect on the planet. It involves manufacturing, developing, promoting, distributing, using, and disposing of the goods and services in a sustainable manner so that the least damage is caused to the environment. Green marketing works on three principles:

- The product should be safe for the environment.
- The product price should be affordable so that many customers can buy it.
- An environmentally conscious marketing strategy should be used to produce, promote, and distribute the goods.

Definition

As per the American Marketing Association (AMA), “Green marketing is the marketing of products and services that are presumed to be environmentally safe.”

As per the Michael Jay Polonsky (1994), “Green marketing consists of all activities designed to generate and facilitate any exchange intended to satisfy human needs or wants, such that satisfaction of

these needs and wants occurs with minimal degradation impact on the natural environment.”

Importance of Green Marketing:

- Green marketing promotes customers to make more sustainable choices by improving their understanding of environmental issues.
- Companies can differentiate themselves from rivals, by promoting eco-friendly products and practices and can attract customers who are increasingly looking for ecologically responsible goods and services.
- It assists companies in reducing their negative impact on the environmental, by promoting goods made from recycled materials.
- Environmentally conscious companies can get the benefit of increased consumer loyalty and a positive brand reputation.
- Companies can create a more sustainable future and promote and contribute to positive change by adopting and supporting sustainable practices through marketing initiatives.

Evolution of Green Marketing:

As per Peattie, the revolution of green marketing is classified into three phases:

- Ecological Green Marketing: concerned with environmental issues and offer remedies for such issues.
- Environmental Green Marketing: concerned with clean technology and innovative products that tackles pollution and waste issues.
- Sustainable Green Marketing: emerged in the 1980s and 1990s, which explain the optimum utilization of resources.

Golden Rules for Green Marketing:

In the modern era of industrialization, green marketing is becoming more important. So the company should try to show the potential customers that they follow green business practices. To make green marketing effective, a company should follow these rules:

Know your customer: Before selling green products, the company must ensure that the customers are aware of the problem that your product tries to solve.

Reassure the customer: Make customers believe that the good performs the same task as it is intended to do. In the name of the environment, they won't forgo product quality.

Being Genuine and Transparent: To create an eco-friendly economy, all relevant information must be published so that the consumers can believe in the legitimacy of the product and precise claims made in regard.

Educate your customers: It is not enough to tell people what companies are doing to safeguard the environment; they should tell them why it is important.

Consider Your Pricing: If you are charging a higher price for your eco-friendly products by making use of high-quality components, make sure that customers can afford the higher price and feel it worthy.

Green Marketing Mix:

Green Product

Green products are designed to reduce the usage of natural resources and lessen the adverse effect on the environment. These products are manufactured from recycled materials or reused goods. These products usually save water, energy, and money. Green products are environmentally friendly products and can be identified using the following criteria:

- Products with natural ingredients.
- Products that are originally grown.
- Products with eco-friendly packaging.
- Products that have no or little harm to the environment.
- Products that are recyclable, reusable, and biodegradable.

According to Michael Peters Group CEO Simon Williams, There are four areas that helps us to define a product as being green: content, structure and packaging, message, and positioning.

Green Price

Price is an important factor because it decides the demand for the product. The price of green products is higher than conventional products because they consider the environmental costs of manufacturing, usage, and disposal. Customers are interested to pay a premium price for the products only if they are getting green benefits from their usage. Further it should increase productivity and should take care of the planet, people and profit. The price of eco-friendly product should be fixed according to the customers' income as well as the products demand so that most customers can buy them and companies can get more profit.

Green Place

The place of a product has a crucial impact on the customer. Very few customers are interested to travel to purchase a product. Therefore, to attract customers, place selection is very important. Green Place aims to reduce carbon footprint and cut down transportation emissions by managing logistics. Green products should be marketed to local, national, and international markets so that customers can easily purchase the products.

Green Promotion

Green promotion should keep in mind the planet, people, and profit while using promotion tools like advertising, sales promotion, directing marketing, public relations, marketing materials, videos, and presentations. Communication with the market should put emphasis on environmental aspects, and promotion of the product should be done in a greener way.

Three kinds of green promotions:

- Discussing a relationship between product/service and biophysical environment.
- Promoting sustainable lifestyles by highlighting a product or service.
- Representing a company's image of environmental responsibility.

Benefits of Green Marketing:

- It helps in acquiring a new market.
- It promotes corporate social responsibility.
- It helps in the optimum utilization and organization of resources.
- It helps to build brand equity and gain customer loyalty.
- It ensures long-term growth with sustainability development.
- It helps to promote eco-friendly innovation and technology.
- It helps in producing recyclable, reusable, and eco-friendly products.
- It helps in saving energy and natural resources and reducing carbon footprint.
- Most employees feel proud and accountable for working in an ecologically conscious organization.

Challenges of Green Marketing:

- It is a modern concept, and many customers are unaware of eco-friendly products, so it is a great challenge for producers to make green marketing successful.
- The majority of customers are not interested to pay higher price for eco-friendly goods because these goods are costly and everyone can't afford them.
- Renewable resources and recyclable materials are used for the creation of eco-friendly products, which are costly.
- It requires eco-friendly technology, so large amount of investment is needed in research and development.
- In green marketing, there arise problems of misleading advertising and false claims, i.e. green washing.
- Educating the customers about the benefits of green marketing is difficult.
- There is no compulsion on customers to purchase the green products.

Types of Green Marketing Strategy:

Green Design

Most crucial green marketing strategy is to develop eco-friendly goods and services at the beginning. Green design is the process of creating goods that are energy-efficient, comfortable, made for long-lasting use, and that meet the reuse, reduce, and recycle requirements. Green design offers a viable alternative to traditional structures by consuming less natural resources and enhancing occupant health and safety.

Green Positioning

It is a strategy for brand positioning in which firms provide information about eco-friendly goods. Green products will not be commercially successful unless their benefits are clearly conveyed. Functional positioning and emotional positioning are the two types of green positioning, both of which are associated with consumer preference for a good.

Green Pricing

It is a crucial strategy for green marketing because it affects the demand for the product. The price of eco-friendly products should be fixed in a way that most of the customers can buy them and contribute to the sustainability of the environment.

Green Packaging

It is another effective strategy for green marketing that helps the company attract customers to buy the product. It is done using eco-friendly materials and production techniques that have a minimal effect on the environment. Biodegradable packaging gives customers an unequivocal indication of the company's commitment to a green approach.

Green Disposal

It takes into account every phase of the products' life cycle i.e. from production to disposal; everything must be sustainable. It is the recycling of old or used products or materials into new ones. Further, it reduces pollution and the release of hazardous materials into the environment.

Green Marketing Strategy Matrix:

As per Ginsberg Jill Meredith and Bloom Paul (2004), there are four types of green marketing strategies for production as well as service companies: Lean Green, Defensive Green, Shaded Green, and Extreme Green.

Lean Green

Lean greens do not promote or market green initiatives. They are engaged in pro-environmental behavior to reduce costs and increase production. In general, they plan long-term preventive initiatives, adhere to strict guidelines, and can't earn substantial profits from the green market. As a result, they work in low-green market and green field with little variations.

Defensive Green

Use green marketing as a preventive measure, a reaction to catastrophes, or as a safeguard against the action of their competitors'. They want to move away from the green market segment, which they regard as a profitable field, to lower the enterprise's image and the costs that may ensue. They take part in lower-level environmental and sponsorship activities. When confronted with rivals or environmental challenges, their low level of green activity will prevent them through advertising or public relations. Unless it has a significant

competitive advantage, it will not launch a green campaign.

Shaded Green

They view green as a chance to create innovative, competitive, and responsive goods. A business has the ability to differentiate itself through green strategies but does not do so. Because they can make a profit by highlighting attributes. They offer direct benefits to the customer, while environmental benefits are promoted as a subsidiary factor.

Extreme Green

Environmental problems are included in all processes of these businesses. The green concept has emerged as a vital corporate pillar. Practices, costs, environmental management, and business process methods are also covered. They continue their activities in the form of niche marketing and provide their customers with products and services through sales channels.

Impact of Green Marketing on Sustainable Development:

Green marketing promotes sustainable development by encouraging businesses and consumers to adopt eco-friendly practices, products, and services and thereby reduce the negative impact on people, planet, and earth. Further, it contributes to sustainable development in three ways:

a) Environmental Impact

- Reduce resource consumption: Using green marketing, businesses can minimize the use of natural resources like raw materials, water, and energy, leading to reduced environmental degradation.
- Minimized Waste: Green marketing promotes sustainable production processes. This leads to minimizing waste and pollution.
- Sustainable Packaging: It helps in promoting eco-friendly packaging materials that are recyclable, biodegradable, or compostable and thereby reduces the burden on landfills.
- Product Design: Green marketing promotes energy-efficient, durable, recyclable, and reusable products, extending their lifespan and minimizing waste.

b) Social Impact

- Consumer Awareness: By raising awareness about environmental issues, green marketing encourage consumers to make informed decision about goods and services on the basis of their environmental impact.
- Community Engagement: Involves community engagement programs, fostering a sense of environmental responsibility and encouraging participation in sustainable activities.
- Ethical Sourcing: It promotes responsible sourcing of materials, ensuring fair labour practices and ethical treatment of workers and producers.

c) Economic Impact

- **Cost Reduction:** Eco-friendly practices help in cost savings by reducing waste, energy-consumption, and material usage.
- **Market differentiation:** It helps businesses attract environmentally conscious consumers by differentiating themselves from competitors, leading to increased market share and brand loyalty.
- **New Market Opportunities:** Green marketing opens up new markets for innovative, sustainable, and eco-friendly products and services.
- **Long-Term Sustainability:** Green marketing contributes to the long-term viability and success of businesses by prioritizing environmental and social responsibility.
- **Innovation:** It creates new business opportunities by driving innovation in sustainable technologies and products.

Green Business operating in India:

Following are examples of green business operating in various sectors in India.

a) Organic farming and sustainable agriculture

- **Nandani Organic:** Produce organic food products, including diary, grains, and spices.
- **Farmizen:** It is a platform that allows people to rent mini farms and grow their own organic products.
- **Green Soul Agro:** Focus on urban farming and organic vegetable production. Promote sustainable practices like hydroponics and vertical farming for growing organic products.

b) Renewable Energy Companies

- **Energia Global:** Specialized in solar, wind and biomass power generation.
- **Greenko Energy Holdings:** Specialized in solar, wind, and hydroelectric power generation.
- **Suzlon Energy:** Wind turbine manufacturer and invests in wind power generation projects.
- **Tata Power Solar:** Manufacture solar panels and provide solar solutions for homes and businesses.
- **ReNew Power:** The largest renewable energy company in India. Specialized in solar and wind energy generation.

c) Sustainable Fashion

- **No Nasties:** Produce 100% organic, fair trade, and vegan cloths.
- **Pippa & Belle:** Create jewellery using recycled metal and gemstones.
- **Soulmate:** Create footwear from natural materials like jute and cotton.
- **Bamboo India:** Create bags and accessories using bamboo, cotton, jute, etc.
- **Khadi Natural:** Produce herbal and organic personal care products like soaps, shampoos and lotions.

d) Sustainable Transportation

- **Ather Energy:** Designs and manufactures electric scooters.

- **Ola Electric:** Promote sustainable transportation through the development of electric scooters and charging infrastructure.
- **Bounce:** Provide bike sharing service by allowing users to rent electric scooters and bicycles for short trips.

e) Waste Management

- **Attero Recycling:** India's leading e-waste recycling company, which provides solutions for e-waste management and material recovery.
- **Banyan Nation:** Recycle plastics and create sustainable packaging materials from them.
- **The Trash Company:** Recycle e-waste and create eco-friendly products like furniture and decor items from it.

f) Eco-friendly Packaging

- **BioD:** Manufacture packaging product from agricultural waste.
- **Bamboo India:** Manufacture packaging product from bamboo.
- **Ecoware:** Manufacture food packaging product from plant based materials like sugarcane pulp and cornstarch.

g) Environmental NGOs and Social Enterprises

- **Aavishkaar:** Provide finance and support facilities to eco-friendly startups in India.
- **SELCO India:** Provide solar energy solutions to underserved areas in India.
- **Barefoot College:** Empower rural communities by providing training in solar engineering and other sustainable practices.

Conclusion:

In today's era, green marketing is a very important concept. It is a tool that protects the nature for future generations by producing eco-friendly products and services. Companies and businesses across the world started adopting this concept to preserve the environment from the adverse impact of industrialization. The development of environmental marketing is still in its initial stage in the market, and more research is required to fully realize its potential. Further it fulfills the condition of 3R - Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle. Moreover, customers are more conscious of environmental issues and are interested to pay a premium price for eco-friendly goods and services. Though successful implementation of green strategy in the global market is very difficult. It is necessary to adopt a green strategy, to preserve natural resources and address environmental problems. For sustainable development, green marketing is only a way.

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